

Relative length, arm ratio, and classification of the chromosomes of *Oryza meyeriana*.

Chromosome number	Relative length (%)	Arm ratio (short/long)	Classification ^a
1	11.80	0.82	M
2	11.48	0.90	M
3	9.87	0.67	SM
4	8.80	0.70	SM
5	8.69	0.73	SM
6	8.31	0.69	SM
7	8.11	0.73	SM
8	7.26	0.63	SM
9	6.97	0.93	M
10	6.79	0.88	M
11	6.17	0.69	SM
12	5.74 ^b	0.37	SAT

^aM = metacentric, SM = submetacentric, SAT = satellite. Arm ratio: M = (1.0–0.76), SM = (0.75–0.25). ^bThe length of the satellite is not included in the length of the chromosome.

A study of Neolithic carbonized rice grains excavated from Hemudu, China

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Rice grains excavated from Hemudu, China (6950±130 BC) are known to be some of the world's oldest remains of rice cultivation. We studied the variation in

these grains to improve our understanding of the origin and domestication of cultivated rice in China.

The length and width of 105 of the grains were measured using an enlarged photograph. About half of the grains were awnless. The grain length ranged from 5.2 to 8.6 mm, with an average of 7.1 mm, and the grain width ranged from 2.1 to 3.2 mm, with an average of 2.8 mm. The grain length-width ratio (L:W) was 1.7-3.2, with an average of 2.6. These findings suggest

that the Hemudu rice population had large variation in grain shape and awn characteristics.

Our earlier study found a few wild rice grains (*O. rufipogon*) among the rice grains excavated at Hemudu.

We therefore infer that about 7,000 yr ago, people in Hemudu did primitive rice cultivation, and that the middle and lower basin of Yangtze River is a homeland of cultivated rice in China. ■

Length, width, and shape distribution of 105 rice grains excavated from Hemudu, China.

Grain trait	Distribution														
Length (mm)	<5.4	5.6	5.9	6.2	6.5	6.8	7.9	7.4	7.7	8.0	8.3	8.6			
(no.)	1	2	3	6	7	21	29	11	9	11	4	1			
(%)	0.9	1.9	2.9	5.7	6.7	20.0	27.6	10.5	8.6	10.5	3.8	0.9			
Width (mm)	2.1	2.2	2.3	2.4	2.5	2.6	2.7	2.8	2.9	3.0	3.1	3.2			
(no.)	2	3	3	1	5	9	20	24	18	15	4	1			
(%)	1.9	2.9	2.9	0.9	4.8	8.6	19.0	22.9	17.1	14.3	3.8	0.9			
L-W ratio	1.7	1.8	1.9	2.0	2.1	2.2	2.3	2.4	2.5	2.6	2.7	2.8	2.9	3.0	>3.1
(no.)	1	0	1	2	5	7	5	12	12	16	13	5	16	4	6
(%)	0.9	0	0.9	1.9	4.8	6.6	4.8	11.4	11.4	15.2	12.4	4.8	15.2	3.8	5.7

Classification of A genome species in the genus *Oryza* using nuclear DNA markers

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We did a new analysis of the restriction fragment length polymorphisms (RFLPs) of 67 accessions of A genome species in the

genus *Oryza*, which contains *O. rufipogon*, *O. nivara*, *O. glaberrima*, *O. barthii*, *O. longistaminata*, *O. glumaepatula*, and *O. meridionalis*, and of the materials previously analyzed by Nakano et al (1992) (see figure). A total of 192 accessions of the A genome species were analyzed.

RFLPs were detected for combinations of *Dra*I-digested total DNA and 21 single copy genomic clones. Genetic distances between accessions were quantified as

$$D = -\ln [2M_{xy}/(M_x+M_y)]$$

where M_x and M_y were the total fragments in accessions X and Y, respectively, and M_{xy} were the common fragments observed between accessions X and Y. A dendrogram was then constructed by the UPGMA method using 64 of the 67 new accessions and 12 previously analyzed accessions as a reference (see figure).

A genome species were classified into five major groups: Asian (*O. sativa*, *O. rufipogon*, and *O. nivara*), *O. glumaepatula*, *O. glaberrima*, *O. barthii*, *O. longistaminata*, and *O. meridionalis*. *O. glumaepatula* had

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Multiple submissions. Normally, only one report for a single experiment will be accepted. Two or more items about the same work submitted at the same time will be returned for merging. Submitting at different times multiple notes from the same experiment is highly inappropriate. Detection will result in the rejection of all submissions on that research.